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UMAR AL-CHAG'MINIY: "AL-MULAKHAS FI AL-HAYA'A" ASARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'rta asrlar Sharq falsafasida tabiiy-ilmiy, falsafiy ilmlar rivojida alohida ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan Mahmud ibn Muhammad al-Chag'miniy va uning "Mulahas fi-l hay'a" asaridagi falsafiy qarashlari borasida mulohaza yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Islom, "Mulahas fi-l hay'a", cosmologik, ilm al-hay'a, xudoning yaratuvchanligi.

UMAR AL-JAGMINI'S: AL-MULAKHAS FI AL-HAY'A

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Abstract: This article discusses the philosophical heritage of Mahmud ibn Muhammad Umar al-Chagmini who played significant role in the development of natural-scientific, philosophical sciences in medieval Eastern philosophy. And he was composed "Mulahas fi-l hay'a"

Keywords: Islam, "Mulahas fi-l hay'a", cosmological, ilm al-hay'a, God's creation

Introduction

The contribution of the Movarounnahr scholars who lived and worked before him in the formation of Chagmini's scientific and philosophical views is enormous.

It is known that in the X-XI centuries in our country there were scientists who made a great contribution to world science with their scientific views and great discoveries. One of them is the great thinker and encyclopedic scholar Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1047), who lived and worked in Khorezm, where Chagmini played an important role in his development as a great scientist. As mentioned above, Beruni was engaged in all the sciences of his time and wrote many works in the natural sciences - astronomy, mathematics, as well as geology, social sciences and humanities. If we look at history, in the late eighth and early ninth centuries, natural knowledge developed rapidly in the Middle East and Central Asia[1]

Materials and methods

The *Mulakhkhaṣ fi al-hay'a al-basīta* was an extremely popular astronomical textbook that played a critical role in the teaching, dissemination, and institutional instruction of Islamic theoretical astronomy. It was composed by Maḥmūd ibn Muḥammad ibn 'Umar al-Jaghmīnī in the early-thirteenth century in the region of Khwārizm in Central Asia; and its study and use as a propaedeutic for more advanced teaching texts is evidenced by thousands of extant copies of the original and its numerous commentaries, super commentaries, and glosses contained in research libraries and various other repositories throughout the world. I have identified fifty-seven treatises that were written to elucidate the *Mulakhkhaṣ*, and these span, conservatively speaking, at least seven centuries beyond Jaghmīnī's original composition date. Indeed, the *Mulakhkhaṣ* was also translated from its original Arabic into Persian, Turkish, and Hebrew, and continued to be taught in earnest well into the nineteenth century.

The study of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* along with its commentaries was still relevant even after "European science" came on the scene, and it is significant that concerted efforts were made to seek teaching approaches that could accommodate the older Islamic scientific traditions such as that of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* along with new (*jadīd*) scientific developments. So Jaghmīnī's ubiquitous introductory textbook on

1 See this article for a list of sixty-one commentaries, supercommentaries, glosses, and translations on various aspects of the *Mulakhkhaṣ*. I should add that according to Zalkida Hadzibegovic, the *Mulakhkhaṣ* was still being taught in Bosnia in the twentieth century [2]

2 Ḥasan al-Jabartī's (d. 1188/1774-75) circle of scholars provides us an excellent example of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* still being studied in eighteenth-century Cairo, and at the Azhar. According to his famous son, the historian 'Abd al-Raḥmān al-Jabartī (d. 1241/182 5-6), his father Ḥasan was a member of the 'ulamā' and attracted students from all parts of the world; and his instruction heoretical astronomy provides us with a significant example with which to understand a vibrant, ongoing scientific educational tradition within Islam.

Included Jaghmīnī's *Mulakhkhaṣ* and Qāzīzāde's *Sharḥ* along with other *hay'aworks* for Jabartī.[3]

Almost a century after Jabartī, the Muslim Ottoman scholar al-Qūnawī (fl. 1857) presents another attempt to reconcile the traditional and *jadīd* science with a quite up-to-date version of the heliocentric system within the context of a traditional astronomical treatise for madrasa scholars[4]

Results and discussion

Having the text of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* should also prove useful for other disciplines, since its influence extends well beyond the discipline of *hay'a per se*;

the treatise's widespread dissemination meant that it crossed multiple borders. For example, there is growing evidence to connect the content of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* with other astronomical disciplines, such as nautical cartography. Jaghmīnī is mentioned in several passages of the atlas of the Tunisian chartmaker al-Sharafī (fl. 1551-79), who attributes his picture of the universe to the “cosmological scheme derived from Jaghmīnī’s treatise on the fundamentals of theoretical astronomy” [5].

A high priority was to ensure that the Arabic edition was as close to Jaghmīnī’s original version as possible. In other words, I was concerned that my edition not be contaminated with the interjections of later commentators and copyists. For example, there was considerable tampering by later copyists and commentators with the parameters for the climes. Thus given the enormous numbers of extant *Mulakhkhaṣ* witnesses, it certainly would be understandable if my goal of providing the “original” text would be met with skepticism. However, there are several reasons that I believe I have been able to reach a text very close to the author’s original. First of all, the advances in digital technology and information sharing meant that I had access to an enormous pool of extant *Mulakhkhaṣ* witnesses to review and analyze.

Mulakhkhaṣ: one contained a dedication by Jaghmīnī to a certain Badr al-Dīn al-Qalānisī along with a dedicatory poem Jaghmīnī composed to him; a second version contained only the dedication (i.e., the poem was omitted); and a third version lacked both dedication and poem. As it turned out, it was this last stripped-down version that would become the most ubiquitous one; and in fact it is this preface that is contained in our earliest known *Mulakhkhaṣ* copy, dated 644.

This is a major problem of the German translation by G. Rudloff and Dr. Ad. Hochheim “Die Astronomie des Maḥmūd ibn Muḥammed ibn ‘Omar al-Ġagmīnī,” *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellscha.* Rudloff and Hochheim unknowingly added numerous comments from Sayyid al-Sharīf al-Jurjānī’s commentary, one of the key witnesses they relied on for their translation. They are certainly not alone in this mistake. So apparently within the relatively short period of forty years after the composition date of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* in 603 H [1206], the dedicatory material was removed from the preface.[6]

Although I knew that these earlier prefaces containing the dedication, with or without the poem, would prove quite significant for dating Jaghmīnī (among other things), I also recognized that there was no guarantee that the contents of any given witness, whatever the preface, had not been changed given the tendency of certain copyists and commentators to modify parameters with “updated” ones. I was able to resolve this potentially serious problem based on the fact that certain parameters in the modified versions of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* came from Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Ṭūsī’s “*Tadhkira fī ‘ilm al-hay’*”a, written over fifty years after the *Mulakhkhaṣ* in 659/1261.

Thus I was able to ignore these witnesses for the edition. Given the relatively small numbers of remaining witnesses that had the unmodified parameters and the original preface (or, lacking this preface, was an early copy), it became a relatively straightforward task to establish the “original” version.

Of course there will always be a few remaining ambiguous readings, and these are noted in the

This was the discovery by Max Krause in 1936 of a copy of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* dated 644 H [1246-7 CE] (“Stambuler Handschriften islamischer Mathematiker,” *Quellen und Studien zur Geschichte der Mathematik, Astronomie und Physik. Abteilung B, Studien 3*

Note that these three different preface versions and the dating of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* are discussed in more detail in both Chapter One and the Commentary.

In addition, these variant prefaces became a convenient tool for helping decide which witnesses to target and obtain for further examination, since repository catalogues often contain incipits within their witness descriptions.

Jaghmīnī’s astronomical work *al-Mulakhkhaṣ*, quoted above, contains ideas very close to Beruni’s views on the structure of the Earth above and its motion.[7]

I discuss this in further detail in my commentary on the second clime. The argument for dating the later versions of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* rests on a scribal error that could only have come after the *Tadhkira* was written. F. J. Ragep points out that even as astute a commentator as *al-Birjandī* (d. 935/1528) was led astray by not realizing that in his dating of *Jaghmīnī* as post-Ṭūsī he was using values for the climes that had been altered; in *Birjandī*’s defense he was writing some three centuries after the *Mulakhkhaṣ*’s composition critical apparatus.[8]

Given the extent of the influence of the *Mulakhkhaṣ* and its impact on the *hay’*’a tradition, it may seem surprising that so little was known about *Jaghmīnī* the man, the scholar, and even the precise location of *Jaghmīn*, assuming it is a location. Rather, the focus has always been on the man’s work, and not the man. Questions such as what kind of society produced such a scholar, what was motivating *Badr al-Dīn al-Qalānisī* to demand an introductory astronomical textbook, and who *Jaghmīnī*’s target audience may have been were left unaddressed.

This led to ambiguity in the literature about when *Jaghmīnī* lived, and even to speculation that there two *Jaghmīnīs*, a thirteenth-century scholar who composed the popular astronomical work *al-Mulakhkhaṣ*, and a fourteenth-century namesake who authored the equally popular medical treatise *al-Qānūnča*. I devote this article to establishing that there was only one *Jaghmīnī* who composed a corpus of scientific textbooks in the late twelfth/early-thirteenth century under the auspices of the *Khwārizm Shāhs* in Central Asia. This includes a review and analysis of the literature on this subject, and I examine the reasons for the ambiguity and why misinformation about the man and his works continues

to the present. I also introduce new evidence to shed light on Jaghmīnī’s actual dates; and perhaps most significant of all, I discuss why dating Jaghmīnī as flourishing in the early-thirteenth century matters—and it matters a great deal. Among the significant reasons I mention is that it directly challenges the prevalent view that this post-Ghazālī pre-Mongol period was one of scientific stagnation (or demise). Jaghmīnī’s example highlights that at least one scholar was composing multiple scientific textbooks and that there was a continuity of scientific learning. It also strongly suggests that the underlying demand for scientific works did not rest with individual initiatives but from the society’s need to promote a scientific education.

In this article I focus on the rich corpus of introductory texts on theoretical astronomy used or potentially used for teaching purposes, which Jaghmīnī inherited and built upon. I include an overview of some formative summary accounts of theoretical astronomy by Jaghmīnī’s predecessors, both Ancient and Islamic, that could arguably have been at Jaghmīnī’s disposal, either directly or indirectly, to use and modify for the *Mulakhkhaṣ*. In addition, in this article I explore the precise meaning of “hay’a” and how the genre of astronomical literature (‘ilm al-hay’a)—which attempted to explain the physical structure of the universe as a whole—came into being in an Islamic context, and how the term evolved. I conclude the article with a summary of what Jaghmīnī does—and does not do—in the *Mulakhkhaṣ* in comparison with some of the earlier works on theoretical astronomy; this is an attempt to address how the *Mulakhkhaṣ* fits into this genre, both content-wise and historically. This discussion is also meant to set the stage for addressing the pressing questions of what inspired the commission of the treatise, and who the target audience was.

In my other article I make the case that the readership of Jaghmīnī’s *Mulakhkhaṣ* was, in the first instance, students studying in madrasas, where his work would have been seen as providing a cosmology glorifying God’s creation. It is my contention that, beginning in the twelfth century, interconnected conceptual and textual transformations began to occur within the discipline of hay’a that transformed the way it was being taught. One very important result is the emergence of a new kind of hay’a textbook that is conducive for a more general audience—hence Jaghmīnī’s *Mulakhkhaṣ* enters the picture, both literally and figuratively. No longer is the study of hay’a restricted only to experts, limited to just a handful of individuals; it now can be used by the ‘ulamā’ to educate the burgeoning number of madrasa students who understood that it offered them another approach to serve God. Astronomy in “the service of Islam,” becomes valued for more than its practical applications for religious ritual (as it most often is depicted); it is valued for its theoretical applications to achieve a better understanding of the physical world of God’s creation. This of course means that major transformations had to have been occurring within the religious institutions; so a more detailed discussion of these transformations and how this term, coined

by David A. King, refers to a notion of science as acting as a kind of handmaiden “in the service of Islam” by addressing only its more utilitarian needs they interrelate ensues.[9] I include a review of some of the evidence establishing that the mathematical sciences (with a focus on astronomy) were being taught in Islamic institutions, especially the madrasas; and also an exploration of some of the reasons that such teaching has often been denied or deemed irrelevant.

In conclusion, I raise the more general issue as to whether the standard approach to the pedagogy of Islamic science tends to promote its history as episodic and dependent in the main on courtly patronage or individual initiatives, both of which tend to place science outside the core institutional structures of Islamic societies. I argue that a serious consequence of this neglects the vital role religious institutions played in sustaining scientific education in premodern Islam

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